

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Annotation: *This article describes the content of the set of competencies that determine the level of development of pedagogical competence that should be acquired by future English language teachers.*

Key words: *professional competence, English language, competence, education, technology, pedagogue.*

INTRODUCTION

Our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "In order for our youth to be independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on the world scale, our state should be happy. and we will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our society" [1], and it is not without attention that the young people of our independent Uzbekistan are focused on free thinking. Therefore, it is one of the high tasks before us teachers to organize lessons based on modern approaches based on the demands of the new era. The only way out of this problematic situation is to introduce a new, competent approach in higher education. Competent approach requires the student to acquire knowledge and skills as a whole, not separately.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Competencies required from future teachers are divided into the following types: - the future teacher should regularly enrich his knowledge, be ready to improve his skills, be aware of current news; - to have the skills and competence to use all types of information communication, information technologies and teaching tools in the educational process; - conscious and independent activity (independent thinking, goal-setting, ability to properly use educational literature and additional resources); - to be able to feel responsibility for one's own actions; - to be able to think critically and positively solve problematic situations that arise in the course of the lesson; - ability to establish pedagogical communication based on cooperation, mutual understanding, empathy, mutual respect and trust; - to have deep

professional knowledge [3]. The level of preparation for the demonstration of competence can be determined according to the following criteria: the idea of self-development and self-expression, preparation for making decisions about choosing a professional path, getting married, having children , readiness to respond to one's own life, independent choice of life path, readiness to form skills in the field of profession, etc.

TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY QUALITIES

- 1 Formation of motivation in students
- 2 Ability to plan, evaluate, and feedback the educational process
- 3 Knowledge of information and communication technologies
- 4 Work on yourself
- 5 To have knowledge of pedagogy and psychology
- 6 Perfect knowledge of his subject
- 7 Innovating the educational environment.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in teaching English, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, the interest in learning a foreign language, the preparation of modern didactic developments based on pedagogical technologies that help to fully satisfy the need. and the development of robust mechanisms for their implementation provides a practical solution to the problem.

REFERENCES:

1. Семина Е.А. (2010). Компетентностная модель выпускника педагогического вуза - будущего учителя математики. Альманах современной науки и образования. - № 5 (36). - С. 133-135.
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bo-lajak-o-qituvchilarning-kasbiy-kompetentligini-rivojlantirishning-pedagogik-shart-sharoitlari>
3. Ishmuhamedov R.J., Yuldashev M.A. Ta'lim va tarbiyada innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar (ta'lim tizimi xodimlari, metodistlar, o'qituvchilar, tarbiyachi va murabbiylar uchun o'quv qo'llanma) - T. 2017, Z68 b .
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bo-lajak-o-qituvchilarning-kasbiy-kompetentligini-rivojlantirish>
5. <https://zenodo.org/record/6482649#.Ys8LsaSW4zQ>